

Online Supplement S1: SO-COM study coding scheme (part B: about the referring oncologist)*

Theme (B):

Intervals of discussing the **referring oncologist/ primary care team** at the referring institute

Within each coded interval, the occurrence of the following 55 potential events was coded:

[Note that 'discussed' can include any utterance regarding the referring oncologist]

- a. **Statements/expressions** by referring provider(s), discussed by oncologist, patient, or relative:
 - Critically (doctor: **sdc** / patient: **spc** / relative: **src**)
 - Neutrally (doctor: **sdn** / patient: **spn** / relative: **srn**)
 - Positive/confirming/defending (doctor: **sdd** / patient: **spd** / relative: **srd**)
- b. **Actions** by referring provider(s), discussed by oncologist, patient, or relative:
 - Critically (doctor: **adc** / patient: **apc** / relative: **arc**)
 - Neutrally (doctor: **adn** / patient: **apn** / relative: **arn**)
 - Positive/confirming/defending (doctor: **add** / patient: **apd** / relative: **ard**)
- c. **Characteristics** referring provider(s), discussed by oncologist, patient, or relative:
 - Critically (doctor: **cdc** / patient: **cpc** / relative: **crd**)
 - Neutrally (doctor: **cdn** / patient: **cpn** / relative: **crn**)
 - Positive/confirming/defending (doctor: **cdd** / patient: **cpd** / relative: **crd**)
- d. **The relation/evaluation of the patient and referring provider(s)**, discussed by oncologist, patient, or relative:
 - Critically (doctor: **rdc** / patient: **rpd** / relative: **rrd**)
 - Neutrally (doctor: **rdn** / patient: **rpn** / relative: **rrn**)
 - Positive/confirming/defending (doctor: **rdd** / patient: **rpd** / relative: **rrd**)
- e. **The inter-collegial relation/evaluation** of referring and consulting oncologist, discussed by oncologist, patient, or relative:
 - Critically (doctor: **idc** / patient: **ipc** / relative: **irc**)
 - Neutrally (doctor: **idn** / patient: **ipn** / relative: **irn****)
 - Positive/confirming/defending (doctor: **idd** / patient: **ipd** / relative: **ird****)
- f. The **oncologist** poses:
an **open question (oq)**, or
a **closed question (cq)** about the referring oncologist or their relationship
- g. The **patient (pq)** or **relative (rq)** poses a **question** concerning the referring oncologist
 - g.1 → What is the first reaction of the oncologist?
 - **Ignore (rdi)**
 - **Acknowledge (rda)**
 - **Exploration (rde)**
 - **Reflection/summarizing (rdr)**
 - Provide **direct information (rpi)**
if the provider directly addresses the patient's/relative's question by uttering statements/actions/ ... about the referring oncologist, use codes above to be more specific; otherwise use the code as is
 - Provide **non-direct information (rpx)**

g.1 was not coded if the patient/ relative kept talking (i.e., the oncologist had not opportunity to react)

** not observed in any SO

*All SO-specific themes that were coded included:

(A) patient motivation, (B) referring oncologist, (C) treatment transfer; for more information, see:

Lehmann, V., E.M.A. Smets, M. de Jong, F.Y.F. de Vos, J.M. Stouthard, and M.A. Hillen, Patient-provider communication during second opinion consultations in oncology. *Patient Education & Counseling*, 2020; **in press**.